

Enhancing Security and Scalability in Electronic Voting through Privacy-Preserving Cryptography and Efficient Data Structures

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Abstract—E-voting systems often face risks such as data breaches, vote manipulation, and lack of voter confidence. Balancing security and anonymity has posed significant obstacles that obscured the immense potential of electronic voting systems. This paper addresses critical challenges in e-voting, including security vulnerabilities, lack of transparency, scalability and user accessibility issues. We propose a privacy-preserving framework to tackle these challenges, enhancing the security, transparency and scalability of e-voting systems. Our framework leverages blockchain to provide a tamper-evident ledger, zero-knowledge proofs to ensure ballot secrecy and data integrity and Merkle Trees to facilitate data storage in a scalable manner. Furthermore, we present findings of the framework’s performance that was conducted under an e-voting use case, while we suggest improvements towards an even more secure and transparent framework.

1. Introduction

Voting systems have evolved during the last hundreds of years to become more sophisticated and complex, starting from paper-based ballots up to electronic voting machines and internet voting which have been introduced as new voting technologies. Traditional paper-based voting faces challenges and fails to address today’s society needs in accessibility, efficiency and costs, with e-voting systems being proposed as a solution.

However, there are also significant challenges that need to be addressed to ensure the security, accuracy, and transparency of e-voting systems [1]. They are vulnerable to hacking, cyber-attacks, and other forms of malicious interference that can compromise the integrity of the election results. In addition, e-voting systems can be subject to technical failures, glitches, and errors that can affect the accuracy of the vote count, while they need to be transparent and provide sufficient safeguards to ensure that voters have confidence in the integrity of the voting process and the results. Finally, they need to protect the privacy of voters and prevent the disclosure of sensitive personal information. To address these challenges, e-voting systems need to be designed with robust

security measures, rigorous testing, and thorough auditing processes. They should also incorporate transparent procedures for verifying and validating the accuracy of the vote count and providing independent oversight to ensure the integrity of the election process.

We aim to revolutionize electronic voting systems by employing a zero-trust architecture and an approach that puts the user at the center of the process from the early phases of the design phase. Our main objective is to tackle main challenges in electronic voting that are still open, such as voter anonymity, ballot privacy, trusted tally/audit as well as verifiability. The proposed framework employs state-of-the-art cryptography for enabling Zero-Knowledge-Proofs (ZKPs), smart contracts to ensure transparency and automation and Merkle Trees for scalability and performance, while following the latest EU guidelines and regulations in terms of digital identities and data protection.

In summary, this paper proposes a privacy-preserving framework for efficient access control and election setup in an e-voting use case. We leverage ZKPs and smart contracts with the overarching goal to revive confidence in electronic voting, empowering citizens to actively engage in shaping their collective future. The subsequent sections are organised as follows. Section 2 presents a thorough review of relevant technologies, laying the foundation for our framework. Section 3 outlines the methodology employed in our research, the proposed architecture and the internal modules of the framework. In Section 4, we present the findings of the performance evaluation, while Section 5 delves into the practical implications of our results and suggests potential avenues for future research. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper, summarizing key findings and highlighting the broader significance of our work in the field of e-voting and beyond.

2. Background

The Background section reviews key concepts and related work, covering existing privacy-preserving techniques and relevant advancements in the field.

2.1. ZKPs and Merkle Trees

ZKPs is a rapidly evolving field in cryptography and have fostered significant advancements in various areas. They have long been established [2], starting from the 90s, when Zero-Knowledge interactive Proof protocols were proposed by Goldwasser et al [3]. Blum et al [4] developed non-interactive zero-knowledge (NIZK) proofs, using shared randomness to create a common reference string (CRS) and to cut out the back-and-forth interaction. Innovation continued with a focus on reducing the size of sent proofs [5], [6]. Groth [7] achieved constant-size proofs by employing pairings to verify polynomial relationships between decoded prover's messages' discrete logs, without needing the actual decoded messages. Following these developments, the Pinocchio protocol [8] significantly improved the efficiency in terms of proof's size, proof generation complexity and CRS setup complexity. Subsequently, the Groth-16 protocol [9] improved Pinocchio's proof size and verifier complexity, utilizing just three group elements in its proof and it has since become the state-of-the-art protocol for scaling and securing transactions [10], [11]. The pivotal strides in achieving non-interactive and succinct zero-knowledge proofs rendered them practically applicable for blockchain systems resulting in several implementations that integrate ZKPs with smart contracts or identity agents.

Alternatives to ZKPs such as Secure Multi-Party Computation (MPC) and homomorphic encryption offer robust solutions. MPC enables multiple parties to jointly compute a function over their inputs while keeping those inputs confidential, ensuring that third parties can collaboratively make computations over the data without revealing individual inputs. On the other hand, homomorphic encryption allows computations to be performed directly on encrypted data, producing an encrypted result that, when decrypted, matches the result of operations performed on the plaintext. Both MPC and homomorphic encryption provide strong privacy guarantees, though each comes with its own trade-offs in terms of computational efficiency and implementation complexity compared to ZKPs.

Merkle Trees are hierarchical data structures composed of hash values, where each intermediate node in the tree represents the hash of its child nodes [22]. They provide significant benefits and find various computer science applications in efficient and secure verification of data integrity over large data sets.

The versatility of Merkle Trees extends across various software domains. They find application in file systems like Btrfs and ZFS, data transfer protocols such as IPFS and database engines including Cassandra and Riak. Particularly within the realm of Blockchains, Merkle Trees play a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency and security of data encoding. Commonly known as "Binary Hash Trees" they offer a robust framework for organizing and verifying data integrity within distributed ledger systems [21].

Several alternatives to Merkle trees exist, each offering distinct advantages. Hash lists provide a simple, sequentially verifiable structure where each node contains a hash of its data and a pointer to the next, ensuring a chain of custody for votes. Binary hash trees, similar to Merkle trees but with specific structural optimizations, and sparse

Merkle trees, which are optimized for space efficiency, offer additional flexibility for different data requirements. Each of these alternatives provides unique trade-offs in terms of complexity, efficiency, and implementation, but Merkle trees are often favored for their established use in blockchain technology, providing robust and effici

The combination of ZKPs with Merkle trees offers a powerful mechanism with strong privacy guarantees and correctness in computations for efficient and scalable privacy-preserving authentication. In this synergy, ZKPs can be employed to prove knowledge of specific data without revealing the data itself, while Merkle trees provide a structure for organizing and verifying the integrity of the underlying data [24].

By constructing a Merkle tree over a dataset and generating ZKPs for specific branches or leaves, one can efficiently prove possession or knowledge of certain elements within the dataset without exposing unnecessary details. This amalgamation is particularly useful in blockchain applications, where ZKPs enhance privacy and Merkle trees facilitate secure and succinct verification of data consistency, providing an elegant solution for confidentiality and integrity in e-voting systems.

2.2. Blockchain and Smart Contracts

Blockchain, a disruptive technology introduced by Bitcoin [13] to facilitate a distributed currency system without the need for a central authority such as a bank or government, leveraging cryptography to ensure security and transaction irreversibility. Following Bitcoin, Ethereum [14] emerged as a significant project that extended Bitcoin's foundational technology by creating the first programmable blockchain with support for smart contracts, thus broadening its applications beyond finance. These immutable pieces of code run on the blockchain, allowing for the automation of processes that affect the blockchain. This provides a high level of programmability and automation while maintaining the auditability and transparency of the executed operations. In subsequent years, various blockchain frameworks have been developed, expanding potential use cases to areas like supply chain management, healthcare record management identity management and protection against fake news.

Blockchains are classified into three major categories based on the permissions to read and write. Public permissionless blockchains claim complete decentralization and security, yet they demand significant resources to function and do not scale efficiently. In contrast, private permissioned blockchains trade off some decentralization for scalability, while still offering lightweight and robust security. Public permissioned are a hybrid type of blockchains that allow anyone to read but only certain organisations or nodes (the validators) to write in the blockchain. Public permissioned blockchains can serve as the basis for establishing trust within an e-voting system, where security and transparency at the same time is required, granting write access only to a set of trusted organisations and allowing everyone to read.

Figure 1. E-voting Use Case

2.3. Related Work

There are several attempts to solve the existing challenges in e-voting through web3 technologies [15], although their adoption and usage are still in their early stages. Voatz [16] is a mobile blockchain-based voting platform that was used in a few elections in the US. However, several concerns about its security and privacy have been risen mainly due to its relation to third parties for the authentication of users and the vulnerability to attacks of the system before reaching the blockchain [17]. Follow My Vote [18] and Agora [19] are solutions that were used sporadically, with their main limitation being that they don't focus on voter anonymity, diverging from EU regulations for data protection.

3. Methodology

The Methodology section outlines the design and implementation details of our privacy-preserving system. It covers the e-voting use case, system architecture, privacy-preserving techniques and the algorithms employed.

3.1. The e-voting use case

The proposed framework follows a privacy-by-design approach enabling trust in electronic voting, where users (Voters or Election Leaders) are at the centre of the system and have full control over their data. More specifically, the examined use case involves 50 Voters who use the framework to remotely participate in a poll without sacrificing ballot secrecy and trust in the tally process.

They use a mobile application to communicate with other actors of the network i.e. Election leaders, authorities and the blockchain, through secure identity agents and encrypted communication channels, as shown in Fig. 1. The mobile identity agents generate and send proofs related to their identity, eligibility to vote or even about their ballot. On the other hand, the Election Leader, uses a web application to setup elections, select eligible Voters and register

Figure 2. Framework's Architecture

data in the blockchain through encrypted interfaces and smart contracts. By integrating smart contracts and ZKPs, we ensure the confidentiality, integrity and transparency of the voting process, while maintaining a user-centered design.

3.2. Framework Specification

ZKPs are a very important asset of the proposed framework towards adhering to most of the e-voting principles [23], i.e. receipt-freeness, voter anonymity, reliability/robustness and verifiability. More specifically, we employ zk-SNARKS (Zero-Knowledge Succinct Non-Interactive Arguments of Knowledge) [25], a specific class of ZKPs known for their efficiency, compactness and the usage of arithmetic circuits. Circuits in zk-SNARKs serve as the formal representation of the computation or logic that needs to be verified, offering a powerful way to validate information without revealing the underlying data. By succinctly conveying proof of knowledge in a non-interactive manner, zk-SNARKs contribute to robust security without compromising computational efficiency.

As shown in Fig. 2, we designed and developed a decentralised architecture to support core functionalities of the e-voting use case, from user management and authentication to the actual casting of the ballot, where the Voter proves her eligibility to vote. The proposed framework uses a smart contract to register users (either Voters or Election Leaders) on-chain using Merkle trees and Election metadata using hashmaps. Users are registered by their (hashed) Ethereum Addresses which ensures their anonymity. Then, proofs are generated off-chain and consequently validated through the Verifier smart contract and over the previously registered data structures. The on-chain Merkle Trees are used for both user and election management i.e. Voters, Election Leaders, eligible Voters for a specific election and Voters that have voted in an election. It should be noted that despite the above complexity of the design, the whole process is completely abstracted from the user point of view, who experiences only the benefits of the architecture which is a trusted and efficient e-voting service. The following subsection describes in detail the zk-SNARKs circuit that was designed and developed.

3.3. ZKP Circuit

A single zk-SNARK Groth16 circuit was developed (written in Circom [26]) that provides three different modes corresponding to different proofs, namely 1) proof of private key possession, 2) proof of existence in User

TABLE 1. CIRCUIT INPUTS

mode	electionId	option	secret	pKey	pathElements	pathIndices
1	0	0	0	645...524	0	0
2	0	0	0	645...524	[...]	[...]
3	5	4	307...454	645...524	[...]	[...]

Management Merkle Tree and 3) proof of existence in Election Management Merkle Tree. The circuit has six (6) input signals *electionId*, *option*, *secret*, *privateKey*, *pathElements*, *pathIndices* and four (4) output signals *election*, *vote*, *hashedAddress*, *root*, while it gets three parameters *n*, *k* and *levels*. The circuit logic, as shown in Algorithm 1, adapts its functionality depending on the values of the input signals, which are checked during the *SanityCheck()* and define the circuit's mode of execution. All input signals are private to safeguard the confidentiality of the user data and are shown in Table 1, while output signals are by nature public.

At first, the circuit executes the *SanityCheck()* to validate the input signals (*electionId*, *option* and *vote*) and ensure their alignment with the expected values. The *CheckBoundaries* function verifies that the *electionId* value is between 2 and 100 (since the 0 and 1 trees are reserved for users), the *option* ranges from 0 to 9 and the *secret* is between 2^{247} and $2^{252} - 1$ (to ensure enough entropy). The *pathElements* signal is an array of hashes representing the Merkle Path, and the *pathIndices* signal comprises an array of binary selectors indicating the left or right position of each corresponding *pathElement* along the Merkle Path.

Next, the circuit calculates the proof of possession of a private key that is associated with an Ethereum Address, through the *EthereumAddress* function, which converts a private key to an Ethereum address. The function receives two parameters as input, *n* and *k*, which represent the bit size of each register and the number of registers, respectively. A private signal - the *privateKey* - is also passed to the function which represents a *k*-length private key, encoded as (x,y) pairs, with each coordinate being encoded with a bit size of *n*. The *EthereumAddress()* function serves as the basis of the entire mechanism and is used to demonstrate ownership of a private key, without ever revealing the actual private key.

Consequently, the *Hasher* function is responsible for the (MiMC) hashing operations within the circuit. It takes two input signals, the *address* - as computed by *EthereumAddress()* - and the *secret*. If the circuit is in mode 2 ($zkVoting == 1$ AND $zkEthereumAddress == 1$), then the *secret* gets a constant value (0 in our case, but could be any other), while if the circuit is in mode 3 ($zkVoting == 1$ AND $zkEthereumAddress == 0$) the *secret* gets the value of the circuit's input signal. The resulting hash is assigned to the *hashedAddress* and the *commitment* output signals.

The final layer of verification entails the *MerkleTree* function, which constructs the Merkle Tree and validates the Merkle proof. This step confirms whether the computed leaf (commitment) aligns with the provided Merkle Path elements and indices, ensuring the commitment's inclusion in the Merkle tree.

As a final step, the circuit loads the output signals with the correct values i.e. *electionId* in the *election*

Algorithm 1 Voting Circuit Template

```

1: procedure ZKVOTING(n, k, levels)
2:   Signal private input electionId, option, secret,
   privateKey[k], pathElem[levels], pathInd[levels]
3:   Signal output election, vote, hashedAddress, root
4:   procedure SANITYCHECK()
5:     checkBoundaries(electionId, option, secret)
6:     if electionId, option, secret == 0 then
7:       zkVoting ← 1      ▷ intermediate signal
8:     else
9:       zkVoting ← 0
10:    end if
11:    if  $\sum_{n=0}^{levels} pathElem + \sum_{n=0}^{levels} pathInd = 0$ 
then
12:      zkEthereumAddress ← 1      ▷
intermediate signal
13:    else
14:      zkEthereumAddress ← 0
15:    end if
16:  end procedure
17:
18:  procedure ETHEREUMADDRESS(n, k)      ▷
converts privateKey to Ethereum address
19:    Signal private input privateKey[k]
20:    Signal output address
21:    address ← PrivKeyToAddr(privateKey)
22:  end procedure
23:
24:  procedure HASHER()      ▷ MiMC hash
25:    Signal private input address, secret
26:    Signal output commitment, hashedAddress
27:    if zkVoting == 1 then
28:      secret ← 0
29:    end if
30:    commitment ← hash(address + secret)
31:    hashedAddress ← hash(address + 0)
32:  end procedure
33:
34:  procedure MERKLETREE(levels)      ▷ calculate
Merkle root
35:    Signal private input leaf
36:    Signal output root
37:    if zkVoting == 1 then
38:      leaf ← hashedAddress : commitment
39:    end if
40:    root ← MTCheck(leaf, pathElem, pathInd)
41:  end procedure
42:
43:  if zkEthereumAddress == zkVoting == 1 then
44:    election ← 0 : electionId
45:    vote ← 0 : option
46:    root ← 0 : root
47:  end if hashedAddress ← hashedAddress
48: end procedure

```

output signal, the selected *option* in the *vote* output signal, the hash of the Ethereum Address in the *hashedAddress* output signal and the *root* of the verified Merkle Tree in the *root* output signal.

3.4. On-Chain Data Logistics

The management of the on-chain data is of crucial importance for the scalability and the security of the system. We have designed and developed smart contracts that efficiently structure the data in the ledger using Merkle trees to enable efficient setup of elections and trustworthy access control.

3.4.1. Election Management. The Election Management smart contract supports the functionalities related to election setup, election management, registration of users and voting. Each of the functions of the smart contract use several modifiers to enhance the function's logic by adding conditions and checks for e.g. the identity of the caller or the validity of the election id. The access control in each function is managed in a privacy-preserving fashion, by using the Verifiers smart contract to verify ZKPs sent by Election Leaders and Voters.

3.4.2. Verifiers. The Verifiers smart contract supports the functionalities of verification of ZKPs. All the logic has been merged into one single function, namely the `verifyProofs()`, which gets as input the zk-SNARK proof and the public output signals of one of the circuit and handles it accordingly.

4. Performance Evaluation

This section provides a comprehensive analysis of our privacy-preserving framework, focusing on its performance aspects. Detailed assessments of system efficiency, in terms of keys size, time for proof generation and gas costs are included below:

1) **Merkle Tree Size:** The size of Merkle trees impacts the time required for their construction within the context of a ZKP circuit. On a 12-core i7 CPU server with 16 GB RAM the generation of a proof with our circuit takes approximately 8 to 10 seconds, including 7 seconds for the calculation of the Ethereum address and the rest 1 to 3 seconds for hashing and calculation of a 32-levels Merkle Tree. Obviously, as the number of levels increases to support more data (users and elections), the computational overhead also increases, however the time required for the Merkle Tree calculation is short proportionally to the rest of the circuit operations.

2) **Scalability vs. Performance Tradeoff:** The generation of keys and circuits introduces a tradeoff between scalability and performance. The more complex calculations included in a circuit the larger constraints will be needed to generate the proving keys, which will be larger in size. The proposed framework produces $\sim 250K$ security constraints which leads to $\sim 200MB$ of proving keys, included in the applications that integrate the ZKP functionality, in our case both the mobile application for the Voters and the web application for the Election Leaders.

3) **Smart Contracts Gas Cost:** Verifying ZKP proofs on-chain incurs significant gas costs, posing a notable

scalability challenge for ZKP-based applications. The gas consumption for our Verifier smart contract can soar as high as 500,000 gas per verification, depending on the proof. Consequently, the proposed framework is suitable for private Ethereum networks where gas costs are much lower or even negligible.

5. Discussion and Future Work

Albeit the security- and privacy-by-design approach of the proposed framework, an e-voting system requires deliberate measures towards paramount security, privacy, scalability and transparency. This section opens the discussion for security considerations and mitigation actions for increased performance that could enhance voter's anonymity, ensure the system's resiliency and most importantly increase citizens' confidence in e-voting.

5.1. Security considerations

The ballot (*vote* output signal) is integrated into the circuit, ensuring its integrity through the ZKP process. This way, the verification of the proof will fail in case someone tries to alter the ballot, since it is part of the circuit. Considering enhancing **ballot secrecy** in the proposed framework, various encryption algorithms could be investigated, with the most prominent one being Homomorphic encryption. The ballot output signal could be encrypted through Homomorphic encryption to ensure that the ballots can be tallied at the smart contracts side, while they remain encrypted. However, its technical feasibility within the context of solidity remains challenging, due to several limitations e.g. gas cost, data handling and resource-intensive computations.

Alternatively, an off-chain approach could be explored, wherein all ballots for a given election are encrypted through Homomorphic encryption, gathered in a server and then results are sent through ZKPs to the smart contract for storage in the blockchain. Moreover, a Layer-2 implementation with Ethereum rollups can be employed that offer more computational resources and lower transaction costs.

Furthermore, in the context of such an e-voting system, **smart contract auditing** by independent security firms is essential for identifying and patching security vulnerabilities that could potentially lead to vote manipulation or linkage of identity through ballots.

Additionally, utilizing **upgradable proxy contracts** allows for the seamless patching of bugs or vulnerabilities in smart contracts without requiring the deployment of new versions of contracts or wiping out data from the blockchain. Upgradable proxy contracts serve as intermediaries that delegate calls to the underlying *implementation contract*, enabling upgrades while preserving contract state and historical data. This approach enhances the agility and maintainability of the voting system by facilitating rapid bug fixes and security enhancements without disrupting ongoing operations.

Finally, employing multiple **proxy contracts per voter**, each delegating calls to the main voting contract, can enhance privacy and security by making it difficult to associate a voter's IP address with their Ethereum address. By distributing voting interactions across multiple proxy

contracts, the linkage between a voter's identity and their voting behavior becomes more challenging to establish, thereby bolstering anonymity and reducing the risk of voter coercion or manipulation. This approach enhances the overall resilience of the voting system against privacy breaches and malicious attacks.

5.2. Smart Contracts

The proposed framework requires a significant amount of gas to run the Verifier smart contract, which renders it suitable only for private networks, as also dictated by the strict security and privacy requirements of an e-voting use case. Mitigating **gas costs** involves optimizing circuit designs, reducing proving key sizes, and exploring alternative verification strategies to alleviate the burden on Ethereum's gas-limited environment e.g. Layer-2 approaches, such as Ethereum rollups, which can be investigated in case there is interest to move to public blockchain networks.

5.3. Proving Keys Size

As mentioned in Section 4, large number of security constraints leads to increased storage requirements that impacts the framework's deployment aspects. Our current implementation is based on circom-ecdsa [27] for the resolution of an Ethereum Address from a private key, however initiatives such as the Spartan-ECDSA [28] aim to mitigate complexities of circom-ecdsa by precomputing certain calculations before circuit compilation, thereby streamlining the overall process and reducing the size of proving keys.

6. Conclusions

While electronic voting promises efficiency and accessibility, challenges like safeguarding voting data integrity, ensuring process transparency and balancing security and anonymity have posed significant obstacles. We propose a privacy-preserving framework that integrates advanced cryptographic techniques such as ZKPs and Merkle trees, coupled with robust access control mechanisms to address anonymity, transparency and scalability issues. Findings of the framework's evaluation in a real e-voting use case are promising and we move forward by prioritising privacy and user experience at the same time.

Acknowledgments

This paper has received funding from the TrustChain Project. Funded by the European Union under GA No 101093274.

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